

Kinetics of Reaction of Triethylammonium Carboxylates with α -Halogeno Carbonyl Compounds in Organic Solvents. Part-4. Effects of Solvents on the Reaction Rate of Triethylammonium Benzoate with Phenacyl Bromide

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Kinetics of the reaction of triethylammonium benzoate with phenacyl bromide in different dipolar aprotic and protic solvents have been followed. The reaction is about 200–400 times faster in aprotic solvent than in protic solvent. In aprotic dipolar solvents the carboxylate anion exists as desolvated one whereas in protic solvents the nucleophile is solvated by hydrogen-bonding thereby decreasing the nucleophilicity of the active species. The correlation of the rate constants with various solvent parameters has been checked.

Carboxylic acids undergo esterification with alkyl halides in the presence of 1,8-diazobicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) or triethylamine with much facility in organic aprotic dipolar solvents¹⁻⁴. The complex formed between the carboxylic acid and amine is found to exist as an ion-pair in aprotic dipolar solvents. Based on the spectral studies it is concluded that the triethylammonium benzoate ion-pair exists in different forms in different solvents. The finer details of the structure of these ion-pairs are decided by the dielectric constant, the solvating power of the medium in which they are present⁵⁻⁸. In solvent of low dielectric constants such as carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane etc., benzoic acid is present as hydrogen-bonded complex. But in solvents like chloroform or acetonitrile, benzoic acid produces unusual species which does not show any identifiable NH^+ absorption, but there is evidence for the ionisation of benzoic acid. In solvents of high polarity like DMSO, the ionisation appears to occur and there is clear evidence of the presence of a species with definite NH^+ absorption. But there is little dissociation of triethylammonium benzoate ion-pair⁵. Our recent kinetic study of the reaction of triethylammonium benzoates with phenacyl bromide in acetone has shown that a hydrogen-bonded ion-pair is the effective nucleophile⁹. The present paper reports the investigation of the solvent effects of the reaction between triethylammonium benzoate and phenacyl bromide. This work is undertaken with a view to understanding by rate study the structural features of triethylammonium-benzoate ion-pair generated in various solvents.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants determined at 30° in several aprotic and protic solvents are presented in Table 1.

There is no appreciable reaction when benzoic acid was treated with phenacyl bromide (a potential substrate for nucleophilic substitution reaction)¹⁰ in the absence of triethylamine. Free unionised benzoic acid (in acetone) was found to be not a potent nucleophile in this reaction. The fact that the reaction has not taken place even in the presence of triethylamine in benzene indicates that triethylamine has not caused the ionisation of benzoic acid. As in carbon tetrachloride or cyclohexane, triethylamine interacts with benzoic acid in benzene by hydrogen bond association with little ionisation to generate the species (I)⁵.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF TRIETHYLAMMONIUM BENZOATE WITH PHENACYL BROMIDE IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Solvent	$10^3, k_2^*$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$
Dimethyl sulphoxide	273
Dimethylformamide	81.6
Acetonitrile	39.9
Acetone	20.3
Tetrahydrofuran	1.45
Dioxan	1.17
Ethylacetate	0.860
Chloroform	0.630
Ethanol	1.17
Isopropanol	1.15
Ethyl cellosolve	0.983
Methyl cellosolve	0.935
Methanol	0.672
Benzene	No reaction
*At 35°.	

The reaction does occur in the solvent like 1,4-dioxan, THF, chloroform and ethyl acetate which

are of intermediate polarity. It is noteworthy that even though dioxan and benzene have comparable dielectric constant values (2.21 and 2.28 at 20°) the reaction fails in benzene and occurs in dioxan. This indicates that the dielectric constant alone is not deciding the reactivity of the active nucleophile. Other solvent properties may play an important role. However, the rates of reaction in the above solvents are much slower than in DMSO, DMF, acetone and acetonitrile, the dipolar solvents with much high dielectric constant values. As expected the highest rate is in DMSO. The rate constant is about 13-fold compared that in acetone. Our previous investigation⁹ led to the conclusion that a hydrogen-bonded ion-pair of the type (II) is the active nucleophile in plain acetone.

Probably a similar species may exist in acetonitrile also. But the precise nature of the nucleophile in DMSO (or DMF) may be different from that in acetone or acetonitrile. Evidence has been presented for the formation $\text{Et}_3\text{NH}^+\text{PhCOO}^-$ in DMSO⁵. This species may exist as tight ion-pair with little dissociation to free ions. However, if the equilibrium,

exists in DMSO, the attacking nucleophile is the free PhCOO^- ion. DeTar and Novak⁵ predicted a dissociation constant of 1.4×10^{-4} for the above equilibrium. The high reactivity of triethylammonium benzoate in DMSO and in DMF is due to anion desolvation, the process which increases the nucleophilicity of the benzoate anion tremendously.

It is evident from the data (Table 1) that the reaction is about 200 to 400 times greater in aprotic solvents than in protic solvents. This is the consequence of two obvious effects: (i) the 'anion desolvation' in aprotic solvents like DMSO which leads to net rate enhancement effect and (ii) in protic solvent through hydrogen bonding which leads to net rate-retardation effect. The rate constant in DMSO is 400 times higher (273×10^{-8}) than in methanol ($0.62 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Alcohols deviate markedly.

It is interesting to note that the rates of the reaction in chloroform (moderately polar solvent) and in methanol (a protic highly polar solvent) are almost similar. Compared to the rate in DMSO

(highest k_a value) the decrease in rate is entirely due to different reasons. It is obvious that triethylammonium benzoate is not existing in similar fashions in these two solvents. The nucleophile (PhCOO^-) is made less potent in methanol due to extensive solvation through hydrogen-bonding and in chloroform, the acid-amine complex may have a pseudo-symmetric structure (III).

Infrared spectral evidence has been reported in support for the presence of structure (III) in chloroform⁷.

The effect of addition of water or ethanol on the rate of the reaction of few aprotic solvents has been investigated and the data are given in Table 2. Addition of either 5% water or 5% ethanol to the aprotic solvent decreases the rate constant in all cases studied. The considerable decrease may be due to the decomposition of triethylammonium benzoate ion-pair (any type), a reactive species, to a solvent-separated ion-pair or to benzoate ion which is highly solvated through hydrogen-bonding by water or ethanol. As expected water causes the rate-retardation to a greater extent than ethanol. This is reflected in the values of k_a/k_{aS} mixed solvent ($k_{aS} = k_{2W}$ or k_{2E}). The solvating power of water is greater than that of ethanol. Addition of water (or ethanol) causes more decrease in the case of acetone or in pure solvent, (k_a/k_{2W}) for acetone and acetonitrile are 1.85 and 2.74, respectively whereas for DMSO and DMF they are 1.34 and 1.17 respectively. Addition of water causes greater decrease in rate in acetone and acetonitrile rather than in DMSO or DMF.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDITION OF WATER OR ETHANOL ON RATE CONSTANT AT 35°

Solvent	$10^8, k_2$	$10^8, k_{2W}$	$10^8, k_{2E}$	k_2/k_{2W}	k_2/k_{2E}
	$\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ pure solvent	$\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ 5% H ₂ O	$\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ 5% EtOH		
DMSO	273	204	217	1.34	1.26
DMF	81.6	69.7	74.2	1.17	1.10
Acetonitrile	40.0	14.6	27.0	2.74	1.48
Acetone	20.3	—	13.1	—	1.55
	15.57 ^a	8.38 ^a	—	1.85	—

^aAt 30°.

Solvents will have specific and non-specific interactions with the solute in a concerted fashion¹¹. So it is profitable to use more than one solvent parameters in the correlation analysis. We have attempted two parameter analysis of $\log k_2$ of

